

PREVENTING LINK ROT IN CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY PRESS'S OPEN-ACCESS SCHOLARLY BOOKS WITH PERMA.CC

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Abstract – Online resources are essential for modern scholarship. In an effort to prevent link rot in Concordia University Press (CUP) books, CUP staff and librarians have partnered to pilot permalink creation using Perma.cc. This paper summarizes the preliminary results of this ongoing pilot, and highlights challenges encountered in the process of creating permalinks for cited URLs in two book manuscripts. We conclude with a discussion of the impact of the project and pathways towards operational implementation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Launched in 2016, Concordia University Press (CUP) is a non-profit academic publisher of peer-reviewed books in Montréal, Canada. An affiliate member of the Association of University Presses and a member of the Canadian Association of University Presses, CUP makes their titles available as free, open-access e-books, as well as for sale in print editions. CUP has been closely tied to Concordia University Library since its inception, with Geoffrey Little, former Associate University Librarian, Scholarly Communications, being a core founder and serving as its first editor-in-chief [1]. The Library

houses the Press's offices and hosts their e-books available through Manifesto, an open-source web publishing platform.¹

In 2024, Ryan Van Huijstee, the Press's Interim Director and Acquisitions Editor, noted that authors were concerned about the risk of link rot—citations of now-dead web-based sources [2]—in their books. To address this problem, the Library's Digital Preservation Committee proposed to pilot the implementation of Perma.cc, a Permalink service developed and maintained by the Harvard Law School Library. As a Perma.cc registrar, Concordia University Library can create Perma.cc accounts and an unlimited number of permalinks—stable URLs—for citation purposes.

Perma.cc is free for academic libraries and the journals and faculty they support. Perma.cc offers some advantages over other free web archiving services. It automatically captures web pages in two forms, a Web ARChive (WARC) file and a PNG screenshot. It also offers the option to save and host a PDF, GIF, JPG, or PNG version of the web page. In addition to saving the live link, Perma.cc provides a short URL as a persistent identifier. It also allows users to manage their links with folders, annotation, and public/private control. Overall, we found Perma.cc to offer a higher quality capture and more

¹ press.library.concordia.ca.

functionality than alternatives like Archive.org's "save page now" feature.

The Library and CUP planned to pilot the service with two book manuscripts that were accepted for publication in early 2025. Librarians would provide training and support for CUP staff to integrate Permalink creation into the editorial process. At the end of the pilot, CUP and the Library will evaluate whether they wish to make this service operational. As of April 2025, the pilot project is well underway, and the rest of this paper will discuss the results so far.

II. PROJECT WORKFLOW

The project team consists of two CUP staff members, a student librarian, and a digital preservation librarian. The workflow for the project is as follows: the digital preservation librarian administers the Perma.cc accounts and provides technical support; the student librarian creates Perma.cc links for URLs cited in the manuscripts; and the whole team meets biweekly to review the Perma.cc links and address questions or issues.

As we figured out the best method and our policies, there was some trial and error which lengthened the time taken. The first manuscript had approximately fifty Perma.cc links that were used and the second thirty-seven, although the number of links created was double that. In general, it took two or three days to create the Perma.cc links and check them, although that time would be reduced in later manuscripts, as would the number of unused (garbage) Perma.cc links created.

First we went through the manuscript, and created Perma.cc links for every URL found. On Perma.cc, there are two ways of creating links – manually or via a browser extension. While the manual method allowed for multiple links to be made at once, that feature was not used. The browser extension proved to be more streamlined and easy to use in most cases (the exception being situations where we uploaded a PDF to replace the webpage). After we exported the links to a .csv file, we went through the spreadsheet colour-coding and double-checking the entries. While we would review the Perma.cc links after creating them, after 24 hours links cannot be deleted. So any mistake that was not caught immediately was saved, for example images or videos that did not load or links created that were

later determined to be unneeded (such as news articles).

III. RESULTS

Scoping was a recurring and challenging discussion topic in team meetings. While our initial approach was to simply create Perma.cc links for all the URLs cited in the manuscript, we quickly found many situations in which this approach did not make sense.

For example, sometimes the web page being cited already had some sort of permalink. In cases where the cited URL was hosted on Archive.org, we decided fairly quickly not to create Perma.cc links, since we consider those URLs to be permanent already. Some citations referenced URLs pointing to a digitized resource hosted on a library website, and upon closer examination of these, they often already had an Archival Resource Key (ARK) or some other persistent identifier on the web page. In these cases, we also decided not to create Perma.cc links and instead update the citation to include the original persistent identifier.

Other cases were less clear cut. Often, when authors mentioned an organization, they provided a link to their homepage in the footnote. When this added little to no information, we had to ask ourselves what the value would be of preserving this page. We found it helpful to think of this question in analogue terms. In a pre-internet book, if an author mentioned an organization, they wouldn't include information like the address or phone number—an interested reader would find that information on their own. In these cases, all a URL is really doing is pointing the reader to a place to get more information about the organization, something they can do easily on their own.

After some back and forth, we decided to only create Perma.cc links for web pages that the author is directly quoting from. We believe this use aligns more closely with the true purpose of the Perma.cc service, which is to allow for the verification of cited information, rather than to serve as a record of a website's existence.

Finally, we also decided not to preserve most online news articles. Our reasoning for this decision was twofold: online news is routinely archived elsewhere, including as part of Library and Archives Canada's national web archive, so we would be

duplicating this work unnecessarily. Also, news article citations typically include enough identifying information, such as title, author, and date, for a reader to locate elsewhere even if the original URL no longer works. We made exceptions for some online-only sources or the online-only component of news sites, such as their blogs, which are not always as rigorously archived as the print editions.

In the process of creating permalinks, we discovered technical limitations where Perma.cc struggled to capture multimedia web content. This was particularly true for embedded videos and audio, which would not replay in a Perma.cc link, or dynamic graphics, although those pages were still preserved for the descriptor text. Similarly, web pages with embedded document viewers or interactive gallery layouts often only captured the first several pages or images of the document. One workaround was to save and upload the pages as PDFs, which worked adequately for still image galleries, but also highlighted Perma.cc's technical allowances. Designed for academic citations, Perma.cc was built for saving text-based resources, but for material that exploited the multimedial, artistic, and interactive aspects of online content, it had trouble. One of the books that we worked on was difficult. It referenced a number of illuminated manuscripts, which often used interactive gallery-style web pages. Due to the difficulties archiving those pages, we were forced to choose particular pages as examples, rather than archiving the entire manuscript.

Finally, our last step was to integrate the permalinks into the manuscripts. We collectively wrote an editorial note, which was inserted after the first instance of a Perma.cc link. For that we followed the Chicago Manual of Style's guidelines, which recommend providing both the original URL, and appending to the end the date archived and the archived link (CMOS 14.104) [3].

IV. CONCLUSION

The project outcomes so far have been successful. We created permalinks for most ephemeral online sources cited in these manuscripts, and we are optimistic that this will significantly reduce the prevalence of these books' future link rot. In a few years, we may be able to measure the quantifiable impact of this work by comparing the prevalence of link rot in these two

books to other CUP books published in the same time frame. In the meantime, we plan to gather informal feedback from CUP stakeholders, including authors and editorial board members, to inform our next steps.

Should a service be operationalized, the practice of creating Perma.cc links would be integrated into the copyediting or manuscript preparation stages. As we assess whether and how to implement the use of Perma.cc operationally, we must consider whether we have the resources to support it long term. For example, the bulk of the labour in this project was completed by a student librarian. This is common practice for special projects at the library, however relying on student workers for ongoing operational processes is not a viable long-term solution.

In the future, this work might be best taken on by a production editor or managing editor, or depending on a publisher's workflow, a freelance copyeditor. While some authors may be able to take on this work for their own manuscripts, a lack of time and training could pose challenges. For authors without an institutional affiliation, cost is an additional barrier to consider.

While Perma.cc's current service model offers free unlimited accounts for academic libraries and courts (individuals and other organizations pay a subscription fee), if Perma.cc decides to charge fees to academic libraries, we will have to decide whether we want to pay for a subscription, switch to a free alternative, or stop creating permalinks altogether, although this will not affect the links already created. In their user guide, Perma.cc clarifies that subscription status does not affect the preservation, access, or visibility of already-made links [4].

Whether or not we use Perma.cc in the future, the lessons learned in this pilot have led to new practices to improve the longevity of URLs in CUP books. While going through the manuscripts we checked and corrected links, such as URLs that changed since writing, and replaced links, particularly those behind paywalls (such as those with library proxies), with persistent identifiers like ARKs and DOIs. Several links had already died, and for those, we provided a link to the most recent version archived in the Wayback Machine.

The fact that some cited links no longer resolved, just in the short period of time since the authors submitted their manuscripts, serves to underscore

the urgency of this work. This project has demonstrated the importance of online resources to modern research, but also how fragile they are.

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